

Structural and magnetic properties of pulsed electrodeposited Fe-Ag alloy

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Abstract : Nanostructured alloy formed by magnetic and nonmagnetic components play a significant role in sensor applications due to their unique magnetic properties. An alloy of the thermally immiscible constituents iron and silver was deposited at three different current densities by pulsed electrodeposition method from a two electrode single bath system containing ferric nitrate, silver nitrate and sodium perchlorate. The surface morphology of the as deposited alloy was investigated using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) analysis while the alloy structure was examined by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD). XRD analysis showed that alloys exhibit *fcc* structure. FESEM analysis reveals that in the deposit, the spherical nanosized particles grow to form dendrites. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy studies indicate the presence of metallic silver and iron. Furthermore, the magnetic properties of samples were characterized on a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) which unveils that the Fe-Ag alloy deposits were ferromagnetic in nature.

Keywords : Pulsed electrodeposition, Fe-Ag nanomaterial, ferromagnetic alloy.

Introduction

The research of nanocrystalline magnetic materials has seen a huge development in the last years. The benefits found in the nanocrystalline alloys stem from their chemical and structural variations on a nanoscale are important for developing optimal magnetic properties. Therefore, many researchers have focused on the preparation of magnetic nanocrystalline alloys consisting of a matrix of non-ferromagnetic and ferromagnetic metals to obtain novel properties such as giant magnetoresistance and superparamagnetism. These materials show larger changes in their resistance on application of an external magnetic field. For this aspect, the nanocomposite combining silver and iron, which are the most immiscible pair of metals with the solubility in both liquid and solid states being well below 1%¹ have important technological applications in single-electron devices², optical media³, or magnetic memory devices⁴ and sensor.

A large number of special techniques have been reported for the synthesis of Fe-Ag alloy including ion implantation⁵, sputtering⁶, thermal evaporation⁷, vapour quenching⁸, gas flow condensation⁹, mechanical alloying¹⁰, chemical reduction¹¹ etc., actually, in practice any

method capable of producing very fine grain-sized materials can be used to synthesize materials. Even so, the above techniques require high cost equipment and have to be maintained at very high temperatures and high vacuum. Furthermore, all these techniques are difficult to calibrate. Hence, a low cost and simple method, like electrodeposition is preferred.

Through electrodeposition, nanoparticles can be coated on different kind of substrates, the size and morphology of the particle can be easily altered and their corrosion¹² and magnetic¹³ behaviour can also be modified. In electrodeposition two types of power source are generally used : the direct current (d.c.) method and the pulse-plating one. In d.c. method only one variable parameter (current or potential) is involved in controlling the quality of deposit. But in the case of pulsed electrodeposition, there are three independent parameters : potential or current, frequency and duty cycle, to control the quality of the deposit. It may result in a smoother, more compact surface, better adhesion on substrate. Moreover pulsed electrodeposition allows electrolysis with a high current density during a short period of ON time followed by even redistribution of ion density during the relaxation

time. This helps to get ultra-fine-grained deposits where the newly deposited ions form new nuclei instead of getting incorporated into the existing particles.

Experimental

Fe-Ag alloy were deposited on stainless steel by Pulsed Electrodeposition (PED). The details have been described elsewhere^{14,15}. The deposition was made with three different current densities 0.18 A/cm², 0.2 A/cm² and 0.22 A/cm² and the deposits were named as sample 1, sample 2 and sample 3 respectively. The electrolyte contains the aqueous solutions of ferric nitrate (0.1 M), silver nitrate (0.01 M) and sodium per chlorate (0.2 M). It also contains the complexing agents like boric acid (0.3 M), and sodium gulconate (0.2 M). After deposition the deposits were rinsed 4 to 5 times with distilled water and finally washed with acetone and dried¹⁶. The as prepared sample was characterized for their elemental composition, crystal structure, magnetic behavior and surface morphology.

Results and discussion

Compositional analysis :

The chemical composition of Fe-Ag alloy deposited at current densities 0.18 A/cm², 0.20 A/cm², and 0.22 A/cm² were dictated by Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analysis using Perkin-Elmer Optima 5300 DV Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP). Atomic percentage of silver and iron in the alloy are found to be 97.31 : 2.69, 56.02 : 43.98 and 96.58 : 3.41 cm² respectively. On comparing the results, it can be seen that only less than 5% of iron deposition is found in sample 1 and 3, whereas in sample 2 the iron content is more than 40%. It indicates that deposition of iron initiates at 0.18 A/cm² and it increases at 0.20 A/cm² and starts to decrease at 0.22 A/cm².

XRD analysis :

The structural analysis of the material was done by using X-ray diffractometer (GE-X-Ray Diffraction system-XRD 3003 TT) with Cu K α ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm). The XRD patterns of the pulsed electrodeposited Fe-Ag coatings obtained at current densities 0.18 A/cm², 0.20 A/cm², and 0.22 A/cm² in their as deposited condition are shown in Fig. 1. These patterns exhibit reflections from (111), (200), (220), (311) and (222) planes indicating the

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the pulsed electrodeposited Fe-Ag coatings.

fcc structure which is similar to the Ag *fcc* structure as per JCPDS file card No. 89-3722. Though the presence of iron in the deposits is ascertained by ICP-OES, XPS and the magnetic studies, the peaks corresponding to the *fcc* silver phase are only detected. Peaks corresponding to neither metallic iron nor iron oxide are observed. These results agree with those reported by Roy *et al.*¹⁷.

The non-observance of iron peaks in the case of sample 1 and sample 3 may be due to lesser percentage of iron content (2.69% and 3.41% respectively) for which no reflection will be obtained but in the case of sample 2 which has about 44% of iron, it may be due to incorporation of iron atoms into the silver lattice, since the atomic radius of iron (0.126 nm) is smaller than that of silver (0.144 nm).

Surface morphology analysis :

FESEM analysis was done to study the morphology of the synthesized Fe-Ag alloy using FESEM equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX) (SU6600, Hitachi) and this image is shown in Fig. 2. The image depicts the clustering of small spherical nanoparticles with sizes in the range of 20 nm to 25 nm, forming dendrites. The size of the dendrites was found to be ~ 85

Fig. 2. FESEM images of Fe-Ag alloy.

nm. The formation of dendrites may be attributed to the use of PED, which leads to the formation of new particles instead of causing an increase in the existing particle size.

Magnetic studies :

Hysteresis loops of the samples were obtained using a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM, EG & G PARC, Model 4500) with a maximum applied field of 7000 Oe at room temperature to study the magnetic property. Fig. 4(a-c) shows the magnetization curves of the Fe-Ag samples. The hysteresis behavior observed for the Fe-Ag

deposits indicates their ferromagnetic nature. The value of saturation magnetization (σ_s) for the sample 1, sample 2 and sample 3 are 0.028 emu/g, 9.1842 emu/g and 0.6313 emu/g, respectively. The saturation magnetization values for different bath composition of Ag-Ni alloy are reported by Santhi *et al.*¹⁵. Fig. 3(a) shows the onset of ferromagnetic nature of Fe-Ag deposited at 0.18 A/cm². Fig. 3(b) shows the weak ferromagnetic nature of Fe-Ag deposited at 0.22 A/cm² and a stronger ferromagnetic nature of Fe-Ag deposited at 0.20 A/cm² is seen in Fig. 3(b) indicating that the magnetic behavior of the samples is in direct proportion with the Fe content in them.

Surface elemental analysis :

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (Omicron ESCA Probe spectrometer with monochromatized Al K α X-rays ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) is used for surface elements analysis, binding energy and oxidation state of iron in Fe-Ag alloy. A shift of 0.45 eV was observed in the spectrum due to the charging effect of sample, as determined from the carbon peak. The binding energy values of the elements in the sample were corrected for this value. The binding energy of Ag is 367.9 eV corresponding to Ag⁰⁺ state. The energy separation between 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2} of iron is observed to be 13.2 eV which agrees good with standard value of metallic iron confirms the existence of metallic iron. The observed value of binding energy peaks at 709.35 eV corresponds to Fe²⁺ oxidation state. The presence of metallic silver, iron and metal oxide is confirmed from XPS measurements.

Fig. 3. Hysteresis loops of Fe-Ag alloy deposited at (a) 0.18 A/cm², (b) 0.20 A/cm² and 0.22 A/cm².

Conclusion

An alloy of the thermally immiscible constituents iron and silver was deposited at three different current densities by pulsed electrodeposition method from a two electrode single bath system. The composition study reveals that iron content in the deposit is found to be maximum at 0.20 A/cm². XRD analysis shows that alloy exhibits *fcc* structure. FESEM analysis reveals that in the Fe-Ag alloy deposits the spherical nano sized particles grow to form dendrites. XPS studies indicate the presence of metallic silver, iron and iron oxide. The vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) study reveals that the Fe-Ag alloy deposits obtained at 0.18, 0.20 and 0.22 mA/cm² are with ferromagnetic activity. The saturation magnetization is found to depend mainly on the iron content in the alloy.

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